

Digital economy in case of demographic regulation of Uzbekistan.

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Annotation: The paper examines the intersection of demographic shifts and the evolution of Uzbekistan's digital economy. It delves into the changing population structure, particularly the role and engagement of women in the economy, and explores the implications for economic development. This article analyzes the share of women in the economy and in which structures they are more capable of work. In what cases the female gender violates the laws. In addition, the demographic policies of some countries are shown, the analysis of gender indicators are described socio-economic growth in Uzbekistan and the concept of demography, social protection, market economy, demographic processes and their factors, sources of studying demographic processes, activism in demographic change.

Keywords: demographic change, population policy, economic growth, growth dynamics, age structure, gender breakdown, country, socio-economic, demographic, valuation, dividend, development, innovation

Introduction

The ancient Chinese philosopher Confucius said two and a half thousand years ago, "If you want to know what kind of people we are, first find out our numbers." These words of the wise man have not lost their relevance even in the current period of social development of Uzbekistan. On the contrary, as the rate of development of our society is rapidly increasing, we should not let the number of our population, its structural and qualitative changes go out of our attention. In this regard, I would like to draw your attention to the number of our citizens who have been living in our country, their recent drastic changes in terms of number and gender, and the future situation of the population in our country in the near and long term.

It is known that with the increasing influence of innovative trends in the national economy of Uzbekistan, the socio-economic significance of demographic changes in our society is increasing year by year. This process depends, first of all, on the rapid growth of the population of our country.¹

Methodology

¹ <https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85122854500&origin=resultslist&sort=plf-f&src=s&sid=270253c0d2f4234f1ec8791f6d03570c&sot=b&sdt=b&s=TITLE-ABS-KEY%28demography+uzbekistan%29&sl=22&sessionSearchId=270253c0d2f4234f1ec8791f6d03570c>

According to the research conducted by a group of foreign economists including Cutler, Poterba, Scheiner, Summers and Akerlof on the USA and East Asian countries, changes in the age structure of the population have caused the growth of per capita income to be significantly higher than the growth of productivity of each employed worker. determined. The reason for the occurrence of such a situation can be explained that changes in the age structure of the population lead to a difference between the population and the growth of the working population of working age. An increase in the working-age population that causes GDP per capita to increase as a share of the total population creates opportunities for economic growth known as the "demographic bonus" or "demographic dividend."²

In her scientific research, the foreign economist Katie Luoma explained the demographic dividend as the economic growth resulting from changes in the age structure of the population, which occurs when the family has many children and has fewer children from the short-lived population to the long-lived population.

The basis of many studies on the demographic dividend is the analysis of demographic pressure, which shows the ratio of the population of working age and non-working age. However, a more detailed analysis of this dividend can be carried out by age group, using information on the average level of consumption and income in a country, comparing it with the composition of the population of that country. This gives a more detailed definition of the number of employees and net transfers required to feed all consumers in that setting at that time.

Empirical studies conducted by demographers in recent years show that it is impossible to determine the economic development of each country without taking into account demographic changes.

² Swai, I. L., & Anasel,

M. G. (2020). What Are They Speaking for: The Relative Participation of Female Councillors on Influencing "Health Related Female Interests" in the Decision Making Processes. *Advances in Applied Sociology*, 10, 11-22.

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Despite improvements in child survival rates in many countries, fertility rates, defined as the average number of children per woman of childbearing age, remain high, especially in less developed countries. Therefore, these countries rarely benefit from the economic benefits known as the demographic dividend. Countries with low birth rates and low death rates will benefit from the demographic dividend, or growth in employment productivity.

Literature review

Robert Malthus (eng. Thomas robert malthus; 1766-1834) is an English clergyman and scientist, demographer and economist, the author of the theory that uncontrolled population growth can lead to a decline in prosperity and mass starvation. His theory is considered by some sources to be the founder of classical macroeconomics due to its influence on John Maynard Keynes (most sources are considered to be the founder of classical macroeconomics).³

Keynes created the original theory of probability based on the assumption that probability is a logical rather than a numerical relationship.⁴ During the Great Depression of the 1930s, Keynes challenged the ideas of neoclassical economics, arguing that free markets would automatically ensure full employment in the short to medium run if workers were flexible in their wage demands. Professor Alexander Ya. Kvasha is one of the creators of the theoretical foundations of the demographic policy in the USSR, an active developer of its goals, principles, measures, effectiveness evaluation methods, and targeted complex programs for population development. He made significant contributions to the study of economic demography and demographic optimality problems.

Demographic Change and Economic Growth in Asia David E. Bloom

Jocelyn E. Finlay-In 1994 the World Bank called East Asia's strong economic growth performance a "miracle". Trade openness, high savings rates, human capital accumulation, and Macroeconomic policy only explained part of this

³ Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. "Thomas Robert Malthus summary". Encyclopedia Britannica, 2 May. 2020, <https://www.britannica.com/summary/Thomas-Malthus>. Accessed 20 November 2023.

⁴ https://biblioclub.ru/index.php?page=author_red&id=1421

growth performance; the remainder Was left unexplained. Research in the ensuing years has shown that when demographic Change in East Asia is taken into account, the miracle is explained. These earlier studies Used the 1960-1990 sample period, but since 1990 Asia has undergone major economic Reforms in response to financial crises and other factors. Moreover, rapid demographic Change has continued in East Asia, and in Asia more generally, with fertility rates falling Below replacement in many of these countries.

Analysis and result

A glance at the diagram provided reveals data on the proportion of distribution by age over fifth year between 2018 and 2022, a particular intriguing highlighted fact by chart was covered 0-4 child`s age about less than 4 billion. During the period age of able to work year by year increased after introducing developing strategy, after the pandemic each age coped with this difficult situation in own way.

The pie chart illustrates the percentage of middle age people by ageing over this period that showed last one. However humanity who live in Uzbekistan almost young people it seem in this circular the highest percentage introducing of teenagers about less than ten.

For example, in the 90s of the last century, the average annual rate of natural growth in Uzbekistan was 27-29 per thousand, but these indicators fell to 14.65 per thousand in 2004 due to certain economic and social reasons during the years of independence. Only since 2004, as a result of positive changes in our economy and society, by 2017, the natural growth rate of our population has increased to 18.15 per thousand. If in 1990 in Uzbekistan 24.3 mln. in December 2018, this number is more than 33.0 million people, that is, it has increased by 35.6%. According to the preliminary data of demographers, by 2050 this figure will be 46-47 million people. (See Figure 1).

Demographic processes, first of all, have a significant impact on the social and labor sphere, and are the main factor of the national economy and society development. has a direct impact on the organization of old-age pension provision.

Picture 1. Changes in the population of Uzbekistan in 2000-2023

Source: 2018 data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Demographic processes are phenomena that reflect the development of the population in time and space, and its increase, death, gender and age composition, as well as changes in the quantity of labor resources, are considered to be phenomena that directly affect the socio-economic development of society and the national economy. It is known that demographic events in society are influenced by general and certain individual random causes. The emergence of certain realities in this process is individual and unique for some reason, but in the demographic process they consist of a sequence of events that change regularly.

Demographic processes under the influence of innovative trends in foreign countries are recognized by leading experts as the most important and relevant factors of humanity at the present time. These issues are becoming especially important in Uzbekistan in the following years. The dynamics of population change, proportional location in all regions, structural structure are often the main factor affecting the formation of strategic factors of economic development of our country and its socio-economic parameters for the future. It is worth noting that the demographic processes of Uzbekistan are developing in a healthy manner in accordance with the current international demographic regulations.

Based on the experience of the world, it is inevitable that Uzbekistan, like all the countries of the world, will see evolutionary processes in the demographic sphere, that is, certain stages of the demographic transition. It is known that the first of them is associated with high birth and death rates, and is characterized by a large number of large families and a rapid change of generations. The second stage is characterized by a sharp decline in death rates due to social progress and health care gains, but a high birth rate remains, leading to rapid and uncontrolled population growth. Uzbekistan, like many countries of the world, has passed the second stage of its demographic development, and is currently in the third stage, due to the growth of the young population and the overall death rate, which is higher than the birth rate.

In world practice, the fourth stage of demographic development is characterized by the death rate exceeding the birth rate and the introduction of the depopulation process, which means that the natural population growth will lead to an absolute decrease of the population due to rapid demographic aging. Naturally, in modern conditions, the process of depopulation threatens and poses a threat to the demographic and social security of the state, because it significantly weakens the resource in terms of resources and causes the population to become dependent on other countries for the formation of labor resources and the level of employment of the population. At the present stage, this process is intensifying in many European countries and the CIS - Russia, Ukraine, and the Baltic republics.

Demographic development is developing unevenly in Uzbekistan due to unstable natural population growth rates. In this regard, compared to world demographic indicators, Uzbekistan has an average indicator among the developed countries of the world due to the natural growth rate falling from 25 per thousand to 15 per thousand.

According to statistics, in the early 2000s, despite the legislative and organizational measures taken by the state to regulate demographic development, the total birth rate varies from 20.50 to 23.66 (Figure 2). The non-development of the "State policy of demographic development" in our country, due to the lack of general registration of the population in the last 30 years, the lack of serious analysis of the situation of the population of Uzbekistan and the lack of prospective forecasts of the demographic development, the birth rate in the country led to the disappearance of the processes of coordination of the size of the family. Only since 2017, special attention has been paid to activities based

on national traditions aimed at strengthening family relations in society, strengthening the health of mothers and the young generation.

Figure 2. Number of births in Uzbekistan in 2000-2017 and total birth rate

Source: 2018 data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The existence of a relatively high birth rate in the country has led to the following situation: today, labor resources in Uzbekistan make up 57.7% of the country's population. According to the indicators of this ratio, Uzbekistan takes the leading place in the world. As a result of fundamental structural changes of the economy under the influence of demographic development and innovative trends, the situation in the labor market is becoming more tense and it is certain that it will become more tense in the coming years.

As of January 1, 2017, out of 18.8 million working resources of Uzbekistan, 14.6 million people are economically active and 4.2 million are economically inactive. 5.3 million of the economically active population. people or 40.2% in the official sector of the economy and 7.9 mln. person or 59.8% work in the informal production sector. This number indicates the current state of the dynamic level of the deepening of the market system of the national economy of Uzbekistan, and at the same time, it indicates the existence of serious problems in terms of the distribution of labor resources in the society at the scale of industry and regions and the efficiency of their use, as well as the level of qualification, gender and age.

Figure 3. Changes in the number of employed population in Uzbekistan in 2000-2022

Source: 2018 data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan

The economy of Uzbekistan faces urgent problems of policy development and implementation in accordance with new, innovative requirements to increase the level of employment of the working population. Taking into account the negative impact of the high level of demographic pressure on the labor market in the future, state programs and measures are being implemented in our country to attract the economically active population to work.

As mentioned above, the republic is in the third stage of the demographic transition, i.e. it is characterized by low birth rate and low death rate due to the structural structure of the young population. Currently, the average age of our population is 25.7 years (men - 25.2 years, women - 26.3 years). The annual natural growth of the population is 450-500 thousand people. [3.15]. A special feature of the age structure of Uzbekistan, which affects the formation of the labor market, is a large part of the population under 30 years of age.

Another important issue for demographic processes is the gradual increase in the share of pensioners in the population of Uzbekistan. One of the main factors affecting the current situation in the pension sector is the structural change in the employment indicators of the population. In particular, the areas of small business and private entrepreneurship include the increase in the flow of labor resources from unstable formal sectors to the private sector, the growth of the

informally employed population expressed in the form of small retail trade, those temporarily employed in informal work mainly in the agricultural sector and other types of service persons. The main feature of the activities of this category is the absence of labor contracts and social security guarantees, regular non-payment of taxes and mandatory allocations to social funds, as well as contributions to the non-budget pension fund of the Republic.

In the near future, the republic is expected to undergo "population aging", that is, the number of people of retirement age will double by 2050, and other gradual and long-term demographic changes are expected. The demographic process of "population aging" is expressed mainly by the fact that the current 30-35-year-olds reach retirement age and the relative lack of replacements. That is, not due to a significant increase in life expectancy, but due to a decrease in the birth rate, in the conditions of a gradual decrease in the birth rate, the population's fertility, the birth rate and the death rate and their ratio are related to the decrease in the death rate in the older age. The above mentioned demographic trends generally correspond to the reproductive potential of the population. The generation of children born in the early 2000s will enter the working age between 2023 and 2030, and the generation of the 1960s will leave the "working" age during this period. This is the main reason for the sharp increase in the number of potential pensioners.

In the medium and long term, according to our estimates, the number of working-age population will continue to grow (the share may reach 10% in 2020, 13% in 2030, and more than 15% by 2040). This growth could significantly increase the demographic "pressure" on the pension system and health care.

In the early 2000s, the pension system in Uzbekistan was not in a bad financial condition, despite the low level of wages and the low amount of pensions. This would allow guaranteed timely payment of pensions and allowances to the segments of the population in need of social protection. During that period, there were more than 4 workers per 1 pensioner, and the average pension amounted to almost 39 percent of the average salary (with a margin of at least 30 percent). As market mechanisms in the economy (inflationary processes, high level of unemployment, increase in the number of workers in the informal sector), the organizational and financial situation of the pension system and the legal framework related to pension payments are becoming more and more tense.

Thus, the demographic trends of recent years accelerate the average aging of the population of Uzbekistan. This trend, in turn, may seriously complicate the financial situation of the population's social protection and pension systems. That is, despite the general stability in demographic development, Uzbekistan, like all developed countries, will enter a period of dangerous increase in its financial pressure on the pension fund and health care systems from 2030.

Conclusion

Based on this point of view, it is necessary to implement the following organizational, legal and financial changes in our national economy and society:

First of all, taking into account the fact that despite the large number of working-age people in the country, their average incomes are still not high, fundamental reform of institutional, legislative and financial mechanisms for the stable operation of the pension system, including raising the retirement age from 2026 (for women - 60, 65 years for men) it is necessary to start implementation step by step.

Secondly, the increase in the standard and quality of life of the population, the organization and operation of jobs specific to innovative technologies, the creation of suitable working conditions for employees, the qualitative change in the content and essence of social and labor relations in society, and the general life expectancy of the population will increase. Improving the quality of medical and educational services in the society helps to increase the social and economic culture of the population, which undoubtedly leads to the stabilization of the demographic structure of the population and a relative decrease in the birth rate of babies.

Thirdly, it is necessary to develop the "forecast of the demographic development of the population of Uzbekistan until 2050" and to adopt the "Concept of the demographic policy of Uzbekistan" taking into account the requirements of the historical traditions and customs of the national spirituality, to prevent negative trends in the maintenance of reproductive health of young families.

Fourthly, it is necessary to create a modern electronic system for rapid monitoring of demographic processes in Uzbekistan, to increase their accuracy and to re-register the population in Uzbekistan in 2022 from the general register.

Fifth, in order to distribute the existing potential of the country's labor resources and to radically increase the efficiency of their use, to analyze the "balance of labor

resources of Uzbekistan's sectors and regions" and develop a forecast of labor resources until 2050.

Sixth, taking into account the prospects of a wide transition to innovative forms and methods of national economic development, further improvement of the system of training of highly educated specialists, the transfer of all higher education systems from a centralized administrative system to the forms of contractual social partners representing the real economy (formation of the order portfolio of universities), mixed financial (in the field of education) budget, contract and order) it is necessary to introduce the mechanism.

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